

14 Abstract

15 Ongoing glacial isostatic adjustment (GIA) is detectable in geodetic height time
 16 series and changes in the temporal gravity field. Global GIA models are often used to
 17 remove these signals from data but quantifying the errors in such models is difficult due
 18 to insufficient knowledge of Earth rheology and past ice history on Earth. Here we de-
 19 scribe how estimates of Earth's temporal gravity field and observed height time series
 20 can be used to quantify errors in GIA models. We tested several GIA models in Fennoscand-
 21 ia, Laurentia and Greenland and found spatial coherence in the pattern of errors, with
 22 RMS velocity errors of ~ 1 mm/yr, ~ 2 mm/yr and ~ 5 mm/yr, respectively. Surprisingly,
 23 there are substantial similarities in the errors of the models tested. Our diagnostic tool
 24 can be used to identify regions where ice histories and/or Earth rheology parameters are
 25 deficient in the GIA models.

26 Plain Language Summary

27 The surface of the Earth continues to move because of melting of very large ice sheets
 28 that existed on Earth 20,000 years ago. These ongoing movements, known as 'glacial iso-
 29 static adjustment' (GIA), cause changes in the strength of Earth's gravity field and are
 30 detectable by the space gravity missions GRACE and GRACE Follow-On. The GIA sig-
 31 nal must be removed from GRACE/GRACE-FO measurements before using them for
 32 quantifying the melting of the Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets. Unfortunately, the
 33 available models used to represent these GIA signals are not accurate. In this study, we
 34 show a relatively simple approach by which the accuracy of the GIA models can be quan-
 35 tified at GPS station locations. Our assessment of several GIA models identifies regions
 36 where they are all accurate but also errors in other locations that are spatially coher-
 37 ent over thousands of kilometers.

38 1 Introduction

39 The Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment (GRACE) and the successor GRACE
 40 Follow-On (GRACE-FO) space gravity missions have sensed changes in Earth's tempo-
 41 ral gravity field since 2002, observing both surficial processes of ice sheet mass loss (e.g.
 42 Tapley et al. (2019), Velicogna et al. (2020)), hydrology cycles (e.g. Rodell et al. (2018))
 43 and solid Earth processes (e.g. Han et al. (2006), Tregoning et al. (2009)). The ongo-
 44 ing response of the solid Earth to melting of polar ice sheets since the Last Glacial Max-
 45 imum, known as 'glacial isostatic adjustment' (GIA), is a key component in all of these
 46 studies, since GIA contributions to GRACE/GRACE-FO measurements must be removed
 47 before mass balance change and/or hydrology studies can be undertaken with the data.

48 These space gravity missions are not the only geodetic observations that sense the
 49 effects of both present-day mass variations and the GIA signals. GIA induces viscoelas-
 50 tic vertical deformation at the surface of the Earth, while short-term mass variations cause
 51 a mostly elastic deformation (Davis et al., 2004). The GIA signals are typically millime-
 52 tres/year in magnitude and essentially linear over decadal - even century - time scales
 53 while the present-day mass variations change on monthly, perhaps even daily time scales.
 54 The sum of these surface deformations is sensed by changes in heights estimated from,
 55 for example, GPS positions (Tregoning et al., 2009).

56 Purcell et al. (2011) showed that, for a wide range of plausible rheological mod-
 57 els and ice histories, there exist a set of viscoelastic Love number ratios that can be used
 58 to calculate present-day surface deformation caused by ongoing GIA. They showed that
 59 their derived values were able to reproduce rigorous computations of GIA to better than
 60 0.2 mm/yr, provided the significant changes in ice loading history had ceased over 5000
 61 years ago. Thus, their approach offers a means of computing present-day GIA vertical

62 movement from spherical harmonic coefficients without the need to invoke a rigorous GIA
63 analysis software.

64 Through a combination of GRACE/GRACE-FO estimates of the temporal grav-
65 ity field and GIA models to represent viscoelastic deformation, it is possible to ‘recon-
66 struct’ a height time series as a sum of elastic and GIA deformation. This procedure is
67 very sensitive to errors in the GIA model representation of viscoelastic contributions to
68 the observed temporal gravity field: over- or under-estimating the GIA component re-
69 sults in the wrong elastic component and can yield highly inaccurate reconstructed height
70 time series when compared to observed height changes (Alvarez Rodriguez, 2024). Thus,
71 the approach provides a tool to assess the accuracy of the GIA models’ predictions of
72 vertical land movement.

73 In this study we assess the accuracy of five GIA models and four GRACE/GRACE-
74 FO estimates of the temporal gravity field against observed height time series at GPS
75 sites in locations of past ice sheets in the northern hemisphere (Fennoscandia, Lauren-
76 tia and Greenland). The approach is predicated on the assumption that the mass changes
77 causing elastic deformation at the GPS sites are sufficiently large-scale as to have been
78 detected by the space gravity missions. This will not always be a correct assumption,
79 meaning that misfits between observed and reconstructed time series may be related to
80 GPS and satellites sensing different signals rather than due to errors in GIA models. How-
81 ever, the errors do tend to be spatially coherent, suggesting that a significant component
82 of the GPS height variations are caused by long-wavelength signals rather than local ef-
83 fects.

84 2 Reconstructed height time series

85 The GRACE/GRACE-FO satellite measurements sense mass change signals caused
86 by both the present-day mass changes (melting ice, variations in rates of snowfall, hy-
87 drological processes) and the ongoing GIA signals occurring within the Earth. Thus, the
88 GRACE/GRACE-FO spherical harmonic coefficients (C^G, S^G) are:

$$C_{nm}^G(t) = C_{nm}^e(t) + C_{nm}^{gia} \times (t - t_0) \quad (1)$$

$$S_{nm}^G(t) = S_{nm}^e(t) + S_{nm}^{gia} \times (t - t_0) \quad (2)$$

89 where C^G, S^G are the Stokes dimensionless GRACE/GRACE-FO spherical harmonic co-
90 efficients that represent the temporal gravity field at time t , $C^e(t), S^e(t)$ are the elastic
91 components of mass change at time t , C^{gia}, S^{gia} are coefficients that represent the rate
92 of GIA, n, m are the degree and order of the spherical harmonic model. The C^{gia}, S^{gia}
93 coefficients are taken from a variety of GIA models, described in Section 3.

94 From just the GRACE/GRACE-FO measurements, it is not possible to identify
95 the spherical harmonic coefficients that represent each of the two different processes. How-
96 ever, these mass variations also cause surface deformation because of both elastic responses
97 to present-day mass changes and to the ongoing GIA. Height changes measured at GPS
98 sites fixed to bedrock will be the sum of these two processes. The vertical elastic defor-
99 mation Δh^e at time t can be computed as (Davis et al., 2004):

$$\Delta h^e(t) = \sum \sum \frac{2n+1}{1+k'_n} P_{nm}(\cos\theta) [C_{nm}^e(t)m\lambda + S_{nm}^e(t)m\lambda] \quad (3)$$

100 where k'_n are elastic Love numbers and P_{nm} are normalised associated legendre functions
101 computed at co-latitude θ .

102 Using the tabulated values of Purcell et al. (2011) for viscoelastic Love numbers
 103 (h_n^{ve}/k_n^{ve}), the vertical viscoelastic deformation Δh^{gia} at time t can be computed as (Purcell
 104 et al., 2011):

$$\Delta h^{gia}(t) = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=0}^n \frac{h_n^{ve}}{k_n^{ve}} P_{nm}(\cos\theta) [C_{nm}^{gia}(t)m\lambda + S_{nm}^{gia}(t)m\lambda] \quad (4)$$

105 A height time series can then be reconstructed as the sum of the elastic and vis-
 106 coelastic deformation:

$$\Delta h(t) = \Delta h^e(t) + \Delta h^{gia}(t) \quad (5)$$

107 A comparison of the observed and reconstructed height time series then yields in-
 108 sights into the accuracy of the GIA spherical harmonic coefficients used and, to a lesser
 109 extent, the GRACE/GRACE-FO spherical harmonic coefficients. If the reconstructed
 110 height time series has a slope that is too large/small then it is likely that the GIA model
 111 has over/under predicted the GIA signal at the GPS location.

112 An example of reconstructed time series is given for a GPS site at Oslo in Fennoscandia
 113 (Figure 1a) and Qaqortoq in southern Greenland (Figure 1b). The reconstructed time
 114 series for the site in Oslo, Norway, agrees with the observed height time series (error <
 115 0.5 mm/yr), with the majority of the reconstructed velocity coming from the viscoelastic
 116 component (Figure 1a). On the other hand, the reconstructed velocity at Qaqortoq
 117 is almost entirely derived from the elastic component and over-estimates the observed
 118 velocity by ~ 1.5 mm/yr. This demonstrates that the GIA model is correct at Oslo but
 119 has under-estimated the actual GIA signal at the site in Greenland.

Figure 1. Observed GPS heights, elastic and viscoelastic components of reconstructed time series at a) Oslo, Norway (OSLS), b) Qaqortoq Greenland (QAQ1). The ICE6G.D GIA model and the CSR mascon solutions were used in the computations for this figure.

120 There is a distinct change in rate in many of the observed - and reconstructed - time
 121 series for sites in Greenland, noticeable around 2013 (e.g. Figure 1b). This corresponds
 122 to an abrupt change in the rate of Greenland ice sheet's total mass loss as recorded by
 123 GRACE, driven by a sudden and very high amplitude change in the North Atlantic Os-
 124 cillation (Bevis et al., 2019).

125 3 GIA models

126 To demonstrate the effectiveness of our tool, we assessed four GIA models in this
 127 study: ICE6G.D (Peltier et al., 2018), the models of Caron et al. (2018) and A et al. (2013)
 128 and the ANU models (Lambeck et al., 1998, 2006, 2010, 2017; Fleming & Lambeck, 2004).
 129 We also include the model of Alvarez Rodriguez (2024), which was derived from an in-
 130 version of GRACE and GPS data rather than constructed using an ice history and rhe-
 131 ological profile of the Earth.

132 Dimensionless Stokes' spherical harmonic coefficients are available for each of these
 133 models and are subtracted from the monthly GRACE/GRACE-FO coefficients (Equa-
 134 tions 1 and 2) to derive corresponding elastic spherical harmonic coefficients for each epoch.
 135 The resulting coefficients are then used in Equation 3 to derive the elastic deformation
 136 for each site at each epoch, while the GIA coefficients, propagated in time to each epoch,
 137 are used in Equation 4 to derive the viscoelastic uplift at each epoch. The sum of these
 138 two deformations then creates the reconstructed height time series at the GPS site lo-
 139 cations (Equation 5).

140 All GIA models tested were created with an assumption of a 1-dimensional viscos-
 141 ity profile (i.e. no lateral variations in viscosity). All GIA models have just one set of
 142 spherical harmonic coefficients which can be used globally with the exception of ANU,
 143 where different viscosity profiles are used to model the viscosity of Fennoscandia com-
 144 pared to Laurentia/Greenland. We used the coefficients appropriate to the location of
 145 the GPS sites when reconstructing time series using the GIA model(s).

146 It is not possible to link the observed elastic component in the GRACE/GRACE-
 147 FO monthly solutions with the elastic deformation observed by GPS through subtract-
 148 ing uplift rates from respective GIA models from the observed GPS height time series.
 149 As outlined in Section 2, the monthly spherical harmonic coefficients of total mass change
 150 must be separated into the elastic and viscoelastic components to then compute, sep-
 151 arately, the elastic and viscoelastic deformation. Therefore, the spherical harmonic co-
 152 efficients representing the GIA model must be subtracted from the GRACE/GRACE-
 153 FO monthly spherical harmonic coefficients (Equations 1 and 2) to then permit the ob-
 154 served elastic deformation to be computed (Equation 3).

155 4 GPS height time series

156 The University of Nevada Reno provides GPS height time series for over 10000 global
 157 sites (Blewitt et al., 2018). We use 398 sites in Fennoscandia, 396 sites in the Lauren-
 158 tide region and 50 sites around the coast of Greenland. Outliers were removed (Alvarez Ro-
 159 driguez, 2024) and, since we assume that deformation is only caused by GIA and/or elas-
 160 tic processes, we did not include sites located in plate boundary regions affected by tec-
 161 tonic deformation or in areas known to be strongly affected by poroelastic hydrological
 162 effects (e.g. Central Valley California (Carlson et al., 2024)). Offsets in the height time
 163 series were estimated using an algorithm that extends the MIDAS velocity approach (Blewitt
 164 et al., 2016) to also identify the timing and magnitude of offsets (Alvarez Rodriguez, 2024).

165 5 GRACE/GRACE-FO temporal gravity fields

166 We used four mass concentration (mascon) solutions as the estimates of the tem-
 167 poral gravity fields: the Center for Space Research solution (CSR, Save et al. (2016)),
 168 the Jet Propulsion Laboratory solution (JPL, Watkins et al. (2015)), Goddard Space Flight
 169 Center solution (GSFC, Loomis et al. (2019)) and Australian National University (ANU,
 170 release RL02, McGirr et al. (2024)).

171 The mascon fields are provided as 0.25 degree (ANU, CSR, JPL) or 0.5 degree (GSFC)
 172 global grids which we converted to spherical harmonic models for each epoch. These are

173 used in Equations 1 and 2 to generate the elastic components that correspond to each
 174 GIA model. Each of these mascon solutions are already corrected for GIA using the ICE6G.D
 175 model (Peltier et al., 2018) and have a degree-1 component inserted. We restored the
 176 GIA correction so that the spherical harmonic coefficients contain the full observed GIA
 177 signal. We also added back the atmospheric pressure signals (Dobslaw et al., 2017) that
 178 were removed by the analysis centers when creating the mascon solutions. The GPS height
 179 estimates are not corrected for atmospheric pressure loading; therefore, adding the AOD1B
 180 atmospheric pressure signals back into the mascon solutions makes the GPS and GRACE/GRACE-
 181 FO information compatible.

182 **6 Results**

183 Reconstructed height time series were created for the total of 844 sites in the three
 184 regions. We then estimated the linear trend of the observed GPS height time series and
 185 the reconstructed time series. We use the difference in these two rates (i.e. ‘observed mi-
 186 nus reconstructed’ velocity difference) as a proxy for the ‘error’ in the GIA modelled vis-
 187 coelastic rate. In this section we applied the GIA assessment tool to all five GIA mod-
 188 els using the four mascon solutions. We calculated the root mean square (RMS) of the
 189 velocity errors separately for Fennoscandia, Laurentia and Greenland.

190 **6.1 Impact of selected GRACE/FO solution**

191 Each of the mascon solutions describe slightly different spatial patterns of mass change,
 192 which may affect the elastic computation of height changes at GPS sites. We can assess
 193 whether these differences are significant and/or whether one mascon solution is more ac-
 194 curate, by computing the velocity errors (and region RMS velocity errors) for each GIA
 195 model and all four mascon solutions (Table 1).

196 Height time series reconstructed using the four mascon solutions tend to be very
 197 similar. For example, the time series for Kulusuk (KULU) in southeast Greenland dif-
 198 fer by < 0.6 mm/yr between the mascon solutions, all of which differ from the observed
 199 rate by ~ 4.5 mm/yr (Figure 2a) due to errors in the GIA model used in the reconstruc-
 200 tion. However, differences between mascon solutions in the spatial patterns of mass loss
 201 do affect the reconstructed time series on occasions, most notably in Greenland where
 202 considerable present-day mass loss is occurring. For example, the GSFC reconstructed
 203 height time series at Qaqortoq (QAQ1) in southern Greenland is quite different from the
 204 other three centers (Figure 2b) which all match reasonably well the observed height time
 205 series, including the significant height increase in 2012. This suggests that the pattern
 206 of mass loss in this area may be less accurate in the GSFC mascon solution. A third ex-
 207 ample in Greenland (L. Bistrup Is Brae P.S, LBIB) shows considerable non-linear mo-
 208 tion in the observed GPS heights and temporally increasing divergence between the four
 209 reconstructed height time series (Figure 2c).

210 There are only minor differences in the regional RMS values produced from the dif-
 211 ferent GRACE/GRACE-FO solutions. It makes little difference in both Fennoscandia
 212 and Laurentia, although the CSR mascon solution perhaps has the smallest RMS in Green-
 213 land. Therefore, for the rest of the paper we discuss results using the CSR solutions.

214 **6.2 Regional comparisons**

215 We used the GIA assessment tool to assess the velocity errors in each area for each
 216 GIA model using the CSR mascon solution. It is clear that the velocity errors are, in gen-
 217 eral, spatially coherent, implying that the underlying causes of error are generated by
 218 signals of broad spatial origin rather than by local signals causing vertical deformation
 219 at the GPS sites (Figure 3).

Table 1. Root-mean-square error (mm) for reconstructed velocities with respect to observed GPS vertical velocities at sites in Laurentia, Fennoscandia and Greenland shown in Figure 3 (and Supplementary Figures S1-S3) for the range of GIA models and GRACE/FO solutions analyzed in this study.

Laurentia				
GIA Model	Mascon Solution			
	JPL	ANU	CSR	GSFC
ICE6G.D (Peltier et al., 2018)	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.6
ANU (Lambeck et al., 2017)	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8
A et al. (2013)	2.3	2.2	2.3	2.3
Caron et al. (2018)	2.1	2.0	2.0	2.1
Alvarez Rodriguez (2024)	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9

Fennoscandia				
GIA Model	Mascon Solution			
	JPL	ANU	CSR	GSFC
ICE6G.D (Peltier et al., 2018)	1.0	1.1	1.0	1.0
ANU (Lambeck et al., 1998, 2006, 2010)	2.0	2.0	1.9	2.0
A et al. (2013)	1.2	1.3	1.2	1.2
Caron et al. (2018)	1.0	1.1	1.0	1.0
Alvarez Rodriguez (2024)	0.9	1.0	0.9	0.9

Greenland				
GIA Model	Mascon Solution			
	JPL	ANU	CSR	GSFC
ICE6G.D (Peltier et al., 2018)	4.5	4.8	4.2	4.6
ANU (Fleming & Lambeck, 2004)	5.9	6.2	5.5	6.0
A et al. (2013)	4.2	4.5	4.0	4.3
Caron et al. (2018)	4.0	4.3	3.8	4.3
Alvarez Rodriguez (2024)	2.3	2.1	2.4	2.3

Figure 2. Comparisons of reconstructed time series using the GIA model of Caron et al. (2018) using the four different mascon solutions at GPS sites in Greenland: a) KULU, b) QAQ1, c) LBIB.

Figure 3. Errors in the reconstructed height time series velocities for Laurentide (top row), Fennoscandia (middle row) and Greenland (bottom row) for a range of GIA models and the CSR GRACE/GRACE-FO mascon solution. Figures using the other mascon solutions are provided in the Supplementary Information. The results shown here are comparable to those of Alvarez Rodriguez (2024), although the latter showed the velocity error as ‘reconstructed minus observed’.

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6.2.1 *Laurentia*

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The pattern of velocity errors in this region effectively delineates the spatial extent of the ice sheet, indicating that all models either over-estimated the amount or timing of ice melt or invoked an Earth rheology that was too strong. While the models are in error by different amounts, they all contain the same overall pattern of negative error beneath the ice sheet and positive error in the peripheral bulge. That is, the models have the peripheral bulge collapsing too quickly and there is too much uplift beneath the ice sheet.

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In contrast, the errors of the model of Alvarez Rodriguez (2024) have the opposite sign. This model did not utilize an ice history, rather it used an implicitly assumed Earth model through the approximation of viscoelastic Love numbers of Purcell et al. (2011). The approach was an inversion of GRACE/GRACE-FO and GPS data using the same theory described in Section 2. As noted by Alvarez Rodriguez (2024), the model works well at locations of GPS sites but does not work well when interpolated into regions with large (i.e. > 200 km) separation between GPS sites.

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6.2.2 *Fennoscandia*

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All GIA models tested over Fennoscandia were found to be accurate to ~ 1 to 2 mm/yr RMS (Table 1). Here we see the reverse of the pattern in Laurentia: the GIA signal is mostly under-estimated under the ice sheet whereas along the peripheral bulge it is mostly over-estimated. This implies that there may not be enough ice lost from the Fennoscand-

240 dian Ice Sheet, or that the rheology is too weak. Either of these scenarios would cause
241 the observed and reconstructed velocities to differ in the pattern seen.

242 Fennoscandia is a region that has a well-distributed GPS network, and the GIA
243 signal seems to be modelled accurately here by all models. The overall RMS in Fennoscan-
244 dia is the lowest of all regions (Table 1), regardless of which GRACE/GRACE-FO so-
245 lution is used. This may be due, in part, to the GPS velocities having been used in the
246 creation of some of the GIA models (e.g. the ICE6G_D model).

247 **6.2.3 Greenland**

248 The velocity errors in Greenland are substantially larger than in the other two re-
249 gions, suggesting that the GIA models are less accurate here. All models derived from
250 ice histories and Earth rheology inputs show positive velocity errors (i.e. observed ve-
251 locity > reconstructed velocity) in the southeast and northwest coasts and negative ve-
252 locity errors along the southwest coast. The magnitudes of the velocity errors often ex-
253 ceed 5 mm/yr, substantially larger than errors found in Fennoscandia and, to some ex-
254 tent, Laurentia. These misfits in velocities are consistent with previous studies which noted
255 that GIA models often do not fit observed uplift rates corrected for elastic loading ef-
256 fects (e.g. Khan et al. (2016)). In addition, because both Laurentia and Fennoscandia
257 have been ice free for millenia, the ice histories required in the GIA models are not as
258 complicated as that for Greenland, which has likely also been affected by the Little Ice
259 Age.

260 The regional RMS value for the Alvarez Rodriguez (2024) model is significantly lower
261 than the other four models. Overall, this model tends to over-estimate the GIA signal
262 slightly, whereas the other four models often under-estimate the signals. We note, how-
263 ever, that the Alvarez Rodriguez (2024) model cannot be interpolated between the avail-
264 able GPS sites accurately because of the large spatial separation between the GPS sites;
265 hence, the model should not be used to correct for GIA in space gravity solutions over
266 Greenland.

267 **7 Discussion**

268 The spatial coherence of velocity errors found between the observed and reconstructed
269 time series provides clear evidence that the GIA assessment tool is identifying errors caused
270 by large-scale deficiencies in GIA models, rather than local effects affecting particular
271 GPS site height estimates. From these insights, regions can be identified where the mod-
272 eling parameters for the Earth rheology and/or ice history need adjustment in the GIA
273 models. These alterations can include modifying in the time of melting, the amount of
274 melting, lithospheric thickness or the viscosity profile.

275 Our GIA assessment tool accounts for both hydrological and GIA rates, whereas
276 using linear rates estimated from GPS heights to constrain GIA models could introduce
277 biases if there are long-term hydrology rates affecting the height estimates. For exam-
278 ple, the reconstructed time series shown in Figure 1b nearly matched the observed time
279 series and the elastic component had a slope of ~ 5 mm/yr. If the observed GPS verti-
280 cal velocity were used to represent the GIA uplift rate then it would be over-represented
281 by this amount, since most of the observed linear rate is actually related to elastic de-
282 formation, not GIA. Our diagnostic tool accounts for the elastic deformation rate; there-
283 fore assesses the GIA model error accurately.

284 Calculating GIA uplift rates using the Love number ratios of Purcell et al. (2011)
285 works well for a large range of rheological models but will be less accurate in regions with
286 very low viscosity, such as West Antarctica, and places with high heat flow in the crust
287 (e.g. Iceland). It assumes Maxwell rheology and that historical changes in ice loads ceased

288 at least 5000 years ago. Therefore, any more recent significant events, such as the Lit-
 289 tle Ice Age (Adhikari et al., 2016), or more complex transient rheology regimes (e.g. Pan
 290 et al. (2024)) could cause inaccuracies in modelling the viscoelastic uplift component of
 291 deformation in GPS heights.

292 The approach assumes that any non-GIA deformation is caused by elastic defor-
 293 mation due to changes in surface loads; therefore, it will not be accurate if any other form
 294 of deformation is present in the GPS height estimates (e.g. tectonic or poroelastic ef-
 295 fects). Furthermore, because very localised changes in water loads are known to affect
 296 local GPS sites more than the broad-scale GRACE/GRACE-FO estimates (e.g. Bevis
 297 et al. (2005)), one can expect similar differences in spatial sensitivity will occur for GPS
 298 sites located to mass changes occurring in small/narrow glacial valleys in, for example
 299 parts of coastal Greenland. This could limit the accuracy of the assessment of GIA mod-
 300 els in such locations.

301 While the approach outlined in this study provides a simple and effective tool to
 302 assess the accuracy of GIA models, it is not possible to use this approach to reverse-engineer
 303 the problem to improve the GIA models. The sign of the misfit of the reconstructed height
 304 time series to the observed height time series (i.e. too high or too low) provides insights
 305 into whether the GIA model requires more ice/stronger viscosity or less ice/weaker vis-
 306 cosity but this information cannot be used to adjust the spherical harmonic coefficients
 307 of the GIA models themselves. Where errors have been identified, the GIA model pa-
 308 rameters - either ice history or viscosity, or both - should be modified and the GIA mod-
 309 els rebuilt.

310 8 Conclusion

311 We have developed a tool to assess the accuracy of GIA models, using observed height
 312 time series and estimates of Earth’s monthly temporal gravity fields. We tested several
 313 GIA models and four mascon solutions and found that, while GIA model errors differed,
 314 similar results were obtained using each mascon solution.

315 The patterns of error indicate that, broadly speaking, GIA models over-estimate
 316 the ice loss for the Laurentide Ice Sheet or use a rheology that is too strong. In contrast,
 317 all models predict present-day GPS uplift rates with a RMS of ~ 1 to 2 mm/yr in Fennoscan-
 318 dia. The errors in models in Greenland are typically larger, although spatial coherence
 319 is clearly evident between models, suggesting similar errors exist in the models’ creations

320 The assessment approach allows spatial areas where GIA models are in error to be
 321 identified and the magnitude of the GIA uplift rate error to be quantified at locations
 322 where height time series are available. While the method can identify shortcomings of
 323 GIA models, it cannot be used to correct the spherical harmonic coefficients of models.
 324 The GIA models must be recalculated by changing ice history and/or Earth rheologi-
 325 cal parameters, but refinements can benefit from insights gained through using our di-
 326 agnostic tool.

327 9 Open Research

328 We used the GRACE and GRACE Follow-On Level-1B data (GRACE-FO, 2019)
 329 to produce the ANU mascon solutions used in this analysis (ANU mascons RL02) (McGirr
 330 et al., 2024). We also used the mascons solutions of CSR version RL06.3 (Save, 2020),
 331 JPL version RL06.3 (Wiese et al., 2023) and GSFC RL06v2.0 (Loomis et al., 2019).

332 Python code to generate reconstructed time series and compare observed and re-
 333 constructed height time series is provided at <https://github.com/paultreg/GIA-Assessment-Tool>,
 334 along with the fortran program (repair_offsets.f90) to identify and correct offsets
 335 in GPS time series. Files for each GRACE/GRACE-FO mascon solution in HDF5 for-

336 mat containing the GPS height time series and reconstructed time series for each GIA
 337 model are provided at <https://github.com/paultreg/GIA-Assessment-Tool>.

338 Acknowledgments

339 The analysis of the GRACE Follow-On data was funded in part through contracts with
 340 Geoscience Australia. R. McGirr was funded by the Australian Research Council Spe-
 341 cial Research Initiative, Australian Centre for Excellence in Antarctic Science (Project
 342 Number SR200100008). We thank G. A. L. Caron, W. Peltier and A. Purcell for mak-
 343 ing available the spherical harmonic coefficients of their GIA models. We thank the peo-
 344 ple and organizations involved in creating the GNET GPS network in Greenland, and
 345 for making the data publicly available. Comments of two reviewers improved the clar-
 346 ity of the manuscript.

347 References

- 348 A, G. R., Wahr, J., & Zhong, S. (2013). Computations of the viscoelastic response
 349 of a 3-d compressible earth to surface loading: An application to glacial iso-
 350 static adjustment in antarctica and canada. *Geophysical Journal International*,
 351 *192*(2). doi: 10.1093/gji/ggs030
- 352 Adhikari, S., Milne, G., Caron, L., Khan, S., Kheldsen, K., Nilsson, J., . . . Ivins,
 353 E. (2016). Decadal to centennial timescale mantle viscosity inferred from
 354 modern crustal uplift rates in greenland. *Geophysical Research Letters*. doi:
 355 10.1029/2021GL094040
- 356 Alvarez Rodriguez, G. (2024). A comparison of vertical land motion observed by gps
 357 and space gravity. *Australian National University Master of Phil. Thesis*. doi:
 358 10.25911/J34E-PP93
- 359 Bevis, M., Alsdorf, D., Kendrick, E., Fortes, L. P., Forsberg, B., & Smalley Jr,
 360 R. (2005). Seasonal fluctuations in the mass of the amazon river sys-
 361 tem and earth’s elastic response. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *32*. doi:
 362 10.1029/2005GL023491
- 363 Bevis, M., Harig, C., Khan, S., Brown, A., Simons, F., Willis, M., . . . T., N. (2019).
 364 Accelerating changes in ice mass within greenland, and the ice sheet’s sensi-
 365 tivity to atmospheric forcing. *Proc. Nat. Adac. Sci.*, *116*, 1934-1939. doi:
 366 10.1073/pnas.1806562116
- 367 Blewitt, G., Hammond, W., & Kreemer, C. (2018). Harnessing the gps data explo-
 368 sion for interdisciplinary science. *EOS*, *99*, published 24 September. doi: 10
 369 .1029/2018EO104623
- 370 Blewitt, G., Kreemer, C., Hammond, W., & Gazeaux, J. (2016). Midas robust trend
 371 estimator for accurate gps station velocities without step detection. *Journal of*
 372 *Geophysical Research*, *121*(3), 2054-2068. doi: 10.1002/2015JB012552
- 373 Carlson, G., Werth, S., & Shirzaei, M. (2024). A novel hybrid gnss, grace, and
 374 insar joint inversion approach to constrain water loss during a record-setting
 375 drought in california. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, *311*, 114303. doi:
 376 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2024.114303>
- 377 Caron, L., Ivins, E., Larour, E., Adhikari, S., Nilsson, J., & Blewitt, G. (2018). Gia
 378 model statistics for grace hydrology, cryosphere, and ocean science. *Geophysi-
 379 cal Research Letters*, *45*(5), 2203–2212. doi: 10.1002/2017GL076644
- 380 Davis, J. L., Elosegui, P., Mitrovica, J. X., & Tamisea, M. E. (2004). Climate-driven
 381 deformation of the solid earth from grace and gps. *Geophysical Research Let-
 382 ters*, *31*(24). doi: 10.1029/2004GL021435
- 383 Dobslaw, H., Bergmann-Wolf, I., Dill, R., Poropat, L., & Flechtner, F. (2017). Prod-
 384 uct description document for AOD1B release 06. *GFZ German Research Cen-
 385 tre for Geosciences Department*, *1*.
- 386 Fleming, K., & Lambeck, K. (2004). Constraints on the greenland ice sheet

- 387 since the last glacial maximum from sea-level observations and glacial-
 388 rebound models. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 23(9-10), 1053–1077. doi:
 389 10.1016/j.quascirev.2003.11.001
- 390 GRACE-FO. (2019). GRACEFO_L1B_ASCII_GRAV_JPL_RL04. version 4.
 391 doi: <https://doi.org/10.5067/GFL1B-ASJ04>
- 392 Han, S.-C., Shum, C.-K., Bevis, M., Ji, C., & Kuo, C.-Y. (2006). Crustal dilata-
 393 tion observed by GRACE after the 2004 Sumatra-Andaman earthquake. *Sci-*
 394 *ence*, 313(5787), 658–662.
- 395 Khan, S., Sasgen, I., Bevis, M., vanDam, T., Bamber, J., & Wahr, J. e. a. (2016).
 396 Geodetic measurements reveal similarities between post-last glacial maximum
 397 and present-day mass loss from the greenland ice sheet. *Scientific Advances*, 2.
 398 doi: 10.1126/sciadv.16009
- 399 Lambeck, K., Anthony, P., Zhao, J., & Svensson, N.-O. (2010). The scandinavian ice
 400 sheet: from mis 4 to the end of the last glacial maximum. *Boreas*, 39. doi: 0
 401 .1111/j.1502-3885.2010.00140.x
- 402 Lambeck, K., Purcell, A., Funder, S., Kjar, K. H., Larsen, E., & Moller, P. (2006).
 403 Constraints on the late saalian to early middle weichselian ice sheet of eura-
 404 sia from field data and rebound modelling. *Boreas*, 35(3), 539–575. doi:
 405 10.1080/03009480600781875
- 406 Lambeck, K., Purcell, A., & Zhao, J. (2017). The north american late wisconsin ice
 407 sheet and mantle viscosity from glacial rebound analyses. *Quaternary Science*
 408 *Reviews*, 158, 172–210. doi: 10.1016/j.quascirev.2016.11.033
- 409 Lambeck, K., Smither, C., & Ekman, M. (1998). Tests of glacial rebound
 410 models for fennoscandinavia based on instrumented sea- and lake-level
 411 records. *Geophysical Journal International*, 135(2), 375–387. doi:
 412 10.1046/j.1365-246X.1998.00643.x
- 413 Loomis, B. D., Luthcke, S. B., & Sabaka, T. J. (2019). Regularization and error
 414 characterization of grace mascons. *Journal of Geodesy*, 93(9), 1381–1398. doi:
 415 10.1007/s00190-019-01252-y
- 416 McGirr, R., Tregoning, P., Purcell, A., & McQueen, H. (2024). Significant local sea
 417 level variations caused by continental hydrology signals. *Geophysical Research*
 418 *Letters*, 51(10), e2024GL108394. doi: 10.1029/2024GL108394
- 419 Pan, L., Mitrovica, J. X., Milne, G. A., Hoggard, M. J., & Woodroffe, S. A. (2024,
 420 03). Timescales of glacial isostatic adjustment in greenland: is transient rheol-
 421 ogy required? *Geophysical Journal International*, 237(2), 989–995. doi: 10
 422 .1093/gji/ggae095
- 423 Peltier, R. W., Argus, D. F., & Drummond, R. (2018). Comment on “an assess-
 424 ment of the ice-6g_c (vm5a) glacial isostatic adjustment model” by purcell et
 425 al. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, 123(2), 2019–2028. doi:
 426 10.1002/2016JB013844
- 427 Purcell, A., Dehecq, A., Tregoning, P., Potter, E.-K., McClusky, S. C., & Lambeck,
 428 K. (2011). Relationship between glacial isostatic adjustment and gravity
 429 perturbations observed by grace. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 38(18). doi:
 430 10.1029/2011GL048624
- 431 Rodell, M., Famiglietti, J. S., Wiese, D. N., Reager, J., Beaudoin, H. K., Landerer,
 432 F. W., & Lo, M.-H. (2018). Emerging trends in global freshwater availability.
 433 *Nature*, 557(7707), 651–659.
- 434 Save, H. (2020). CSR GRACE and GRACE-FO RL06 mascon solutions v03.
 435 doi: 10.15781/cgq9-nh24
- 436 Save, H., Bettadpur, S., & Tapley, B. D. (2016). High-resolution csr grace rl05 mas-
 437 cons. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, 121(10), 7547–7569. doi:
 438 10.1002/2016JB013007
- 439 Tapley, B. D., Watkins, M. M., Flechtner, F., Reigber, C., Bettadpur, S., Rodell, M.,
 440 ... others (2019). Contributions of grace to understanding climate change.
 441 *Nature climate change*, 9(5), 358–369. doi: 10.1038/s41558-019-0456-2

- 442 Tregoning, P., Ramillien, G., McQueen, H., & Zwartz, D. (2009). Glacial isostatic
443 adjustment and nonstationary signals observed by grace. *Journal of Geophys-*
444 *ical Research*, 114(B6). doi: 10.1029/2008JB006161
- 445 Velicogna, I., Mohajerani, Y., Landerer, F., Mougintot, J., Noel, B., Rignot, E., ...
446 Wiese, D. (2020). Continuity of ice sheet mass loss in greenland and antarctica
447 from the grace and grace follow-on missions. *Geophysical Research Letters*,
448 47(8), e2020GL087291. doi: 10.1029/2020GL087291
- 449 Watkins, M. M., Wiese, D. N., Yuan, D.-N., Boening, C., & Landerer, F. W. (2015).
450 Improved methods for observing earth's time variable mass distribution with
451 grace using spherical cap mascons. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid*
452 *Earth*, 120(4), 2648–2671. doi: 10.1002/2014JB011547
- 453 Wiese, D. N., Yuan, D.-N., Landerer, F. W., & Watkins, M. M. (2023). JPL
454 GRACE and GRACE-FO mascon ocean, ice, and hydrology equivalent wa-
455 ter height CRI filtered RL06.3Mv04. Ver. RL06.3Mv04. *PO.DAAC*. doi:
456 10.5067/TEMSC-3JC634